

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Using more complex cover crop mixtures may lead to higher marketable yields

Organic farmers rely on soil biology to make their system work (digesting organic materials, providing nutrients and controlling soilborne diseases). Cover crops play an important role in their fertilization plan for capturing nitrogen and carbon and stimulating soil life with root exudates. The use of species diverse cover crop mixes could improve the soil biology and lead to higher yields of main crops.

In a field trial conducted over 4 consecutive years, 4 different cover crop mixes were compared:

1. Phacelia and Black Oat: A standard without legumes.
2. Phacelia and Egyptian Clover: A legume + non-legume.
3. 5-Species Mix: A moderately diverse mix including legumes.
4. 12-Species Mix: A highly diverse mix including legumes.

This comparison took place on an organic managed plot, where non-inversion tillage has been employed for several years

and fertilisation happened with cattle farmyard manure. Only in Season 2 no fertiliser was applied (Season 1: 227 kg Ntot/ha manure + 50 kg Ntot/ha fertilizer pellets, Season 3: 239 kg Ntot/ha manure and Season 4: 158 kg Ntot/ha manure). Throughout the years (Season 1: broccoli, Season 2: red beet, Season 3: potato and Season 4: leek), the marketable yields of the main crops were recorded (next to the non-marketable yield and the harvest residue).

Interestingly, there was a trend towards increased marketable and total biomass yields when species diverse mixes were used (5- and 12-species, most notable in season 2 and 3). Although no significant differences were measured, the observed trends largely aligned with trends in cover crop biomass and in average nitrate nitrogen availability. Further research could provide deeper insights into these findings.

1. Average percentage difference compared to the annual average marketable yield (%) over the trials years in function of the choice of cover crop mixture.

KEYWORDS

Cover crops, organic agriculture, marketable yields

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